

To Know Which Type of Medication We Need to Prescribe, We Need to Know the Type of Population that We Have Nowadays

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Abstract

This study aims to show that the type of population that we are attending to nowadays is very different from the past caused of the modernization of telecommunications after the implementation of 4G and 5G technology. The human body is composed of energy, the part of energy that is visible and the part of energy that is invisible to the naked eye. In a research made by myself analyzing 1000 patients' energy of the five internal massive organs of traditional Chinese medicine, from 2015 to 2020, I concluded that 90% of them, independent of the age group and independently on the type of diagnosis, were in the lowest level of energy. These energy systems present inside the body are responsible for all functions and without energy, our body cannot survive. Depending on the type of medication that we will treat this patient if we will highly concentrated medication, the internal energy will drop even more and can worsen the patient's condition or can lead to the death of this patient. For this reason, in this study, I am showing that, due to this energy alteration in the five internal massive organs of the Liver, Heart, Spleen, Lungs, and Kidney, the medication of choice to be used in this new type of population that we have nowadays are highly diluted medications, according to Arndt-Schultz Law, created in 1888 by two German researchers. The conclusion of this study is to show that, depending on the type of population that we have nowadays, we need to prescribe medications according to them. The use of highly diluted medications are the medications of choice to be used nowadays, due to these alterations in the energy pattern in the five internal massive organs of the five elements theory of traditional Chinese medicine.

Keywords: Five elements theory; Traditional Chinese medicine; Homeopathy.

1. Introduction

Since the implementation of the Flexner report in 1910, medical schools had to teach that only medicines produced by the pharmaceutical industries would be considered "scientific" and therefore, the other medicines used at the time were banned from medical schools such as homeopathy and phytotherapy. [1]

However, with the process of modernizing of telecommunication, with the implementation of cell phones, and the use of computers, there was a change in the energy pattern of the human being. [2]

According to Albert Einstein (1879-1955) everything that exists in the universe is composed of energy and so is the human being. [3]

The energy part is in the constant transformation from its invisible to visible part and vice versa. And our body, there is also the energy part, which is studied by the most ancient medicines such as Ayurvedic medicine and traditional Chinese medicine. [4]

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In the article written by me (2021) whose title *The Influence of Cell Phones and Computers on Our Immune System*. I am emphasizing the adverse effects caused by the chronic and prolonged use of cell phones and computers nowadays, leading to a state of immunosuppression due to the energy drop in our massive internal organs. [5]

I have a patient who was about 70 years old when she got a cell phone from her daughter to use her Facebook page. [5]

Before she got the device, I measured her energy and she still had energy in her five internal massive organs, however, after she started using her cell phone frequently when measuring her energy, there was a change in the result of this exam, becoming the organs totally without any energy, different from before. [5]

In a survey carried out in my clinic from 2015 to 2020, analyzing the internal energy of the five internal massive organs, I concluded that 90% of all my patients seen at that time were completely without energy in the five internal massive organs that are the Liver, Heart, Spleen, Lung, and Kidneys. [6]

The function of these organs according to Chinese medicine is to produce energy to maintain our survival, so that the Blood flow inside the blood vessel occurs, and if there is a stop in the production of this energy, various symptoms may occur in the various medical specialties, as all symptoms in all specialties come from the same energy imbalance, therefore, each imbalance can generate several symptoms, but each symptom can result from several energy imbalances. [4]

Each internal massive organ is responsible for one external sensory organ. For example, the Liver is responsible for the eye and vision. The Heart is responsible for the tongue and communication. The Spleen is responsible for the mouth and sense of taste. The Lungs are responsible for the nose and sense of smell. The Kidney is responsible for the ear and hearing process. Also, the immune system depends on energy and if the organs are not producing enough energy, we are very immune deficient and not immune competent. [7, 8]

In this case, where the energy part is compromised, and it does not show up in the exams in the initial stages, a person may be suffering from some symptoms but their exams may come back normal. This often happens when there are couples who want to have children but they cannot and they do tests and nothing changes. The problem is usually in the energy part, which is deficient most of the time and the non-treatment of this deficiency can cause failures in the treatment in question since energy deficiencies are invisible to the naked eye. [9]

Therefore, the prescription of drugs must be in accordance with the type of population we have today, characterized by a population with very low internal energy and if we continue to prescribe highly concentrated drugs, we will inevitably have complications generated by this type of drug, because according to the Ardent-Shultz law, created in 1888 by two German scientists, the use of highly concentrated medication can cause greater energy deficiency and thus even cause the patient's death. The same we will have with vaccines nowadays, as they also cause a drop in energy, and in this way, all the energies responsible for maintaining the flow of Blood within the blood vessel will no longer exist, causing stagnation of Blood within the blood vessels, It is very common these days, with increasing rates of myocardial infarction in young patients, stroke, thromboses or even sudden death. [10-12]

Therefore, due to this change in the energy of the world's population, the medicine of choice for this new energy situation of everyone, including newborn children, is homeopathic medication, and in this way, it increases the energy of patients and should be the medicine of choice. The choice for use in any treatment, as today, the use of highly concentrated drugs is inadequate for this current population. [13]

Changes to medical school curricula must be made as these institutions are only teaching their future doctors to prescribe highly concentrated medication in all specialties. [1]

And these drugs are no longer suitable for the COVID-19 pandemic, mostly highly concentrated drugs were used in an already very energy-deficient population. I question whether the deaths were really caused by the virus or by the type of medicine used to treat the patients. [13-15]

As I have been studying the energy pattern of my patients since 2010, I already knew that patients with COVID-19 could not be receiving these types of drugs and also could not receive this type of vaccine, as they are having many side effects or even dying after using these treatments. [16, 17]

2. Conclusion

The conclusion of this study is to demonstrate that, depending on the energy of the population, we need to prescribe medications that could not harm even more the internal energy of the five massive organs of the five elements theory of traditional Chinese medicine. The energy of our population changed dramatically caused of chronic exposition to electromagnetic radiation and for this reason, we need to choose highly diluted medications to treat our patients instead of highly concentrated medications to fit the type of energy present in our patients nowadays.

Compliance with ethical standards

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